

The Impact of E-Training System on Employees' Job Performance

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ABSTRACT: The development of information and communication technology has made e-training a vital function of human resource management within any organization, especially in recent years. Reliance on this type of training has increased to invest in human assets and help employees acquire new skills and knowledge, develop their current skills, increase their productivity and raise the quality of their performance in the work environment. The aim of this paper is to explore the impact of the E-Training System dimensions (Efficiency – Methods – Environment) on employee job performance. It is a quantitative study that uses an electronic questionnaire as a data collecting tool from a sample of (103 employees) working in private sector companies in the Egyptian market. The main findings demonstrated that the perceived E-Training dimensions (Efficiency – Methods – Environment) has a positive impact on Employee Job performance. Moreover, it also showed that perceived E-Training efficiency (content & trainer) is the most significant predictor for employee job performance, followed by the E-Training environment. However, there were no significant differences in employees' perceptions of (a-E-Training Efficiency b- E-Training Methods c- E-Training Environment) according to their gender, educational level, and age groups.

KEYWORDS: Human Resources Management Practices (HRMP), E-Training, Job Satisfaction, Productivity, Job Performance

1. Introduction

In a competitive world, organizations are facing increased challenges due to globalization. They strive to achieve success and differentiate themselves from competitors in the same industry. So, organizations have to attract the best talent for their human resources and utilize them effectively (Bafaneli & Setibi 2015, 239). According to Wolor et al. (2020, 444), human capital is seen as a valuable commodity that contributes to the growth of the company's market value, it is one of the most effective resources of any company and the basis of its success and continuity. Therefore, organizations must invest in and develop these resources on an ongoing basis, to gain a competitive advantage over competitors (Kazi et al. 2019, 3).

There is no doubt that managing the human element is the main function of human resource management within any organization, as it is responsible for attracting and motivating employees, managing their skills and talents efficiently, achieving job satisfaction, and retaining them. So, organizations need effective management of human resources, as they affect the achievement of organizational goals; through its function in preparing an effective system for training and developing the employees and workers of the organization (Kazi et al. 2019: 3).

Moreover, the awareness of employees has developed, and their sense of responsibility has increased towards enhancing their current skills and adding new skills to meet the needs and tasks of the work, and they become more eager to take advantage of the available training opportunities to ensure their employability or to move to a better place, or to advance within the organization in which they work (Karam 2019, 195; Kazi et al., 2019: 3; Mikołajczyk 2022, 546).

Advances in information technology have led to an increased reliance on e-training models in the last few years. According to Asamoah and Avenorgbo (2021, 35), E-training is defined as a remote training process through the use of the Internet or Intranet, which helps

individuals acquire the knowledge and skills they need to improve their performance in various disciplines and aspects of general knowledge. Companies' demand for this type of training has grown; to achieve many advantages such as saving travel expenses, flexibility, availability of diverse content, continuity of training and learning, enhancing worker performance and increasing the number of trained employees, and competitiveness. So, the main objective of e-training is to enhance job performance and create a productive workforce. (Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia 2016, 2; Yang & Lin 2021, 459). Moreover, for many individuals, e-training is seen as the preferred learning medium due to its universal accessibility (Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia 2016, 2).

Accordingly, this paper seeks to identify the impact of the E-Training System dimensions on employee job performance, in the private sector companies operating in Egypt. The following are the objectives of this study:

- a) To examine employees' perceptions of E-training (Efficiency – Methods – Environment).
- b) To assess the impact of E-training (Efficiency – Methods – Environment) on employees' job performance.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Human Resource Management Practices (HRMP)

Employee performance refers to how an employee goes above and beyond his/her responsibilities. Several studies have shown that employee performance has a significant impact on job satisfaction, as high-performing people feel more fulfilled and happier at work, which is reflected in the company's performance and long-term profits. (Top et al. 2020, 51; Zardasht et al. 2020, 49).

HR practices are defined as a set of internally coherent and consistent practices for which they are designed to enhance employee efficiency, motivation, and commitment (Najam et al. 2020, 2). It is also defined as planned practices aimed at the effective management of human capital (Kadiresan et al. 2015, 163). Therefore, these practices enable companies to become more effective to achieve outstanding business performance and gain a competitive advantage in the market (Domínguez-Falcón et al. 2016, 491; Elrehail et al. 2020, 126).

Human resources (HR) are a vital resource for any organization, and effective management of these resources can help the organization achieve its goals and objectives (Elrehail et al. 2020, 126). Therefore, the essential role that Human Resource Management (HRM) plays in determining business survival, effectiveness, and competitiveness is just as important as making a profit. Human resource management practices have helped support any company's business strategy, as companies maintain and increase competitive advantage through strategic human resource management that depends on the quality and competence of their employees (Chong et al. 2020, 121; Beijer et al. 2021, 4).

According to (Najam et al. 2020: 3), the main areas of Human Resources Management Practices (HRMP) include (1) employee skills, which includes selection and recruitment; (2) motivation, which includes performance-based appreciation; and (3) empowerment, which includes equal participation rights. This study will focus on human resource management practices related to the E-training system and its impact on employees' job performance and productivity at work.

2.2. E-Training

2.2.1. Definition and Characteristics

The process of training and developing employees within any organization is a reciprocal process with great impact. It helps the organization achieve its goals with the required efficiency and quality, and on the other hand, it helps the employee to develop and feel a sense of achievement

and positive self-satisfaction, raise his productivity and increase his level of performance (Govand & Shukur 2015, 66; Khan et al. 2016, 34).

The concept of training refers to all procedures for learning experiences and activities that aim to increase the effectiveness of performance and behavior, by acquiring new skills, knowledge, and experiences (Govand & Shukur 2015, 66). Training is a short-term intervention that aims to transform people by providing them with the required and adequate information, skills, and attitudes to meet or exceed customer expectations and accomplish outcomes. It is also defined as an organized and systematic activity that leads to an increase in the skills, knowledge, and competence necessary to carry out job tasks effectively (Khan et al. 2016, 34). In the same context, Maršíková & Šlaichová (2015, 14) defined training as a planned effort by the organization to facilitate employee learning of job-related competencies.

With regard to e-training, it is similar to e-learning in some characteristics, such as technology usage and content delivery method, but the training takes a much shorter period to achieve a specific educational goal or acquire a specialized skill (Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia 2016, 1). E-training can be defined as a remote training process through the use of the Internet or Intranet, which gives the trainees the required knowledge and skills on the various selected topics. So, the term e-training refers to the use of multimedia technologies, the Internet, and modern means of communication to provide interactive training programs that suit the needs of the target group of trainees in various fields and overcome the conditions of time and place (Amara & Atia 2016, 3).

It is clear from the above that e-training is the process of acquiring a set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes, and this process is characterized by a set of characteristics such as the reliance on modern technological means, interaction, flexibility, connectivity, diversity of knowledge sources, variety of means of content delivery, saving time, effort, and cost (Amara & Atia 2016, 5; Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia 2016, 2).

2.2.2. E-Training Importance

Due to globalization, many companies have started to rely on e-training due to its ability to reach large groups of target audiences in different regions or countries at a lower cost and with varied methods that suit target audiences from different fields and disciplines. Moreover, for many individuals, e-training is a preferred channel of learning due to its universality, accessibility, and availability. (Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia 2016: 1; Asamoah & Avenorgbo 202, 35).

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused economic closures and the management of commercial and service activities via the virtual environment; as a way to limit the spread of the virus. These circumstances made organizations face the challenges of training their employees to enhance their performance, so they turned to the electronic training system. Since then, organizations have been interested in developing their technological infrastructure to keep pace with the rapid changes that occurred in the learning and training environment (Asamoah & Avenorgbo 2021, 34). Therefore, the importance of e-training and skills development for employees has increased, as organizations have found themselves in need of developing the skills of their employees, especially technological skills; This led them to search for new methods and tools to develop the performance of their employees and train them remotely (Mikołajczyk 2022, 545).

Learning is a continuous process in which an individual improves his knowledge and skills, which must evolve with technological development and job requirements. An employee who is suitable for his current job, and believes that he is stable in his work and does not need to learn new skills, may face new job challenges to improve performance or productivity, which can be removed through training (Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia 2016: 1; Khan et al. 2016, 34). Therefore, many organizations have recently resorted to e-training to develop the efficiency of their employees to reach the appropriate required levels at a lower cost and greater flexibility. Where training can identify and distinguish skills gaps in the organization; it is the gap that arises due to the difference between the skills and abilities that

employees possess and the skills and abilities that the organization wants them to have or require (Oluwaseun 2018, 184; Karam 2019, 193).

2.2.3. E-Training Dimensions

This study sheds light on the dimensions of e-training, which include the efficiency of E-Training in terms of the efficiency of the trainer and the content he provides, e-training methods, and the e-training environment, as follows (Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia 2016, 2; Karam 2019, 195; Asamoah & Avenorgbo 2021, 35,37):

- E-training efficiency (trainer and content): it means the extent to which the content of the training programs is updated, well-designed, and matches the training needs. Moreover, the extent to which the trainer's experience in his field of specialization, his skills in presenting the content, and his ability to design relevant training activities. Besides, the trainer's skills in managing programs and interacting with participants.
- E-training methods: e- training has a variety of methods and tools that can use. The selection of the most appropriate ones depends on the specific needs and goals of the training program, and the organization's resources and technological capabilities. Examples of these methods include the use of computer-based operation networks, interactive platforms, internet worldwide websites, video and multimedia, and electronic applications. These methods of delivery help employees to engage in a long-term learning process because training is not just providing information, but practice, application, and feedback.
- E-training environment: The e-training system is meaningful to employees when IT support and other maintenance infrastructure services are available at the company. Moreover, when it is easily accessible, efficient, has flexible schedules and activities with work tasks, and has a facilitated and motivating learning environment.

2.3. E-Training and job performance

Job performance means achieving a goal or set of goals within a job. It is not a single job but intertwined activities and tasks. Job performance is a separate behavior from the results of a particular job and is related to success and productivity (Top, Abdullah & Faraj 2020, 51).

Globalization has led many companies to use e-learning and e-training strategies in an attempt to create a competitive advantage, meet the demand for learning, align the needs of their employees with strategic organizational goals, in addition to the fact that companies use various Internet applications and distance learning has become an indicator of the extent to which these companies have developed. And its ability to keep pace with the requirements of the competitive global market (Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia 2016, 1; Mikołajczyk 2022, 548).

According to Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia (2016, 2), the use of e-training by employees had varying associations with job productivity and job performance. It turns out that the use of technology alone will not lead to the desired results, where companies should provide administrative support and motivation side by side with providing e-training opportunities for their employees. Therefore, companies must evaluate the benefits of this type of training and its return on job performance to justify continuing investment in these training programs. It is necessary to know whether the employees are satisfied with the e-training system provided by the organizations or not. Do they have the self-motivation to pursue e-training in the future, and will the targeted benefits be achieved (Wolor et al. 2020, 445)?

Regarding, the relationship between job training satisfaction and job performance, it means how employees feel about the aspects of job training they receive, in terms of their attitudes towards the degree to which training activities and programs fit their job level, the extent to which they can develop their knowledge and skills, and the extent to which they help them perform job tasks efficiently and effectively. Moreover, some studies have indicated the positive effect of employees' training satisfaction on their overall job performance. It also

affects their attitudes towards the organization they work at in terms of commitment, participation, and job citizenship, and they are less inclined and less willing to work in other organizations (Khan et al. 2016, 35; Huang 2019, 11; Nguyen & Duong 2020, 375).

3. The Research Model and Hypothesis

Based on the above literature review, this study proposed a model that explains the correlation hypothesis of the study as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The Proposed Research model

H1: Perceived E-Training efficiency (Content & Trainer) has a positive impact on an employee's job performance.

H2: Perceived E-Training methods have a positive impact on an employee's job performance.

H3: Perceived E-Training environment has a positive impact on an employee's job performance.

4. Research methodology

4.1 Research sample

The current research is a descriptive study based on primary and secondary methods of data collection. The study relied on a quantitative research design because it aims to achieve the research objectives by testing the validity of its hypotheses. In this study, an online questionnaire used to collect primary data from the respondents; since this study is quantitative and is concerned with collecting data and converting it into numerical values.

The population of this study was the employees across different fields working in the private sector companies operating in Egypt; and who had experience in using e-training at their workplace. The total sample was determined based on the number of participants in the online survey. A total of (103) questionnaires were submitted back and used in the final analysis. Therefore, purposive sampling under non-probability sampling is applied. A non-probability sample is arbitrary, and we typically select it subjectively with put a pattern or scheme in mind. In purposive sampling, the researcher selects specific cases, which are more typical of the population, and includes them in the study sample. This type of sampling is very useful in situations where you need to reach a target sample quickly and where sample proportionality is not the main concern (Picardi & Masick 2013, 156).

4.2 Instrument Development

This section provides details about the instrument used, which is an online questionnaire, to collect data in order to test the validity of research hypotheses. The questionnaire consisted of two separate parts; the first part was regarding participants' demographic characteristics and job information questions. The second part was divided into questions related to employees' perceptions of E-training dimensions (Efficiency- Methods- Environment), and questions related to employees' job performance.

The researcher used five-point Likert scales ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The questionnaire statements were adapted from different sources. The statements of questions regarding employees' perceptions of the E-training system dimensions (Efficiency - Methods – Environment) adapted from (Govand & Shukur 2015, 69; Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia 2016, 4; Asamoah & Avenorgbo 2021, 39). In terms of questions regarding employees' job performance; the statements adapted from (Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia 2016, 5; Nguyen & Duong 2020, 379).

5. Data Analysis Results

5.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Demographic information of respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	60	58.3	58.3	58.3
Female	43	41.7	41.7	100
Total	103	100	100	

Age Group	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
20-30	61	59.2	59.2	59.2
31-40	28	27.2	27.2	86.4
41-50	10	9.7	9.7	96.1
Above 50	4	3.9	3.9	100
Total	103	100	100	

Educational Level	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Bachelor's Degree	84	81.6	81.6	81.6
Postgraduate	19	18.4	18.4	100
Total	103	100	100	

Monthly income	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 5000 LE	26	25.2	25.2	25.2
5000 LE- less than 10000 LE	22	21.4	21.4	46.6
10000 LE- less than 15000 LE	30	29.1	29.1	75.7
10000 LE- less than 15000 LE	15	14.6	14.6	90.3
Above 20000 LE	10	9.7	9.7	100
Total	103	100	100	

5.2. Reliability Test

To test the reliability of questionnaire statements used in this study, Cronbach's alpha was used, with the following results: E-Training Efficiency (Content & Trainer) 0.799, E-Training Methods 0.803, E-Training Environment 0.751, and Employee Job performance 0.894. Thus, alpha ranged from 0.89 to 0.75, exceeding the minimum standard for reliability of 0.70 recommended by Picardi & Masick (2013, 51), which is a satisfactory level. Table 6 summarizes these results.

Table 2: Reliability

Variable	Reliability Statistics Cronbach's Alpha	NO. of items
E-Training Efficiency (Content & Trainer)	0.799	4
E-Training Methods	0.803	6
E-Training Environment	0.751	5
Employee Job performance	0.894	7

5.3. Validity Test

Content validity assesses whether the content is representative of all aspects of the construct and reflects the measurements. To produce valid results, the content of a survey or measurement method must cover all relevant parts of the subject it aims to measure (Patten & Newhart 2017, 126). The questionnaire of this study contains a series of questions and measurements. It has been validated by submitting it to the academic supervisor for reviewing and suggesting the required adjustments before publishing it online to be filled out by the target group.

5.4. Hypothesis Testing Results

H1: Perceived E-Training efficiency (Content & Trainer) has a positive impact on employees' job performance.

Table 3: Linear Regression test of E-Training Efficiency against Employee Job performance

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.605	.366	.359	.48724		
ANOVA						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	13.813	1	13.813	58.185	<.001
	Residual	23.978	101	.237		
	Total	37.791	102			
Coefficients						
Model	Standardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	
1	(Constant)	1.662	.309		5.383	<.001
	E-Training Efficiency	.599	.079	.605	7.628	<.001

Dependent Variable: Employee Job Performance

Predictors: (Constant), E-Training Efficiency

A simple linear regression was performed to determine how much variation in Employee Job Performance is explained by perceived E-Training efficiency (Content & Trainer). By reviewing the ANOVA table, the findings showed that the model is significant

($P < .001$). According to the results of the model summary table, perceived E-Training efficiency ($R = .605$, $R^2 = .366$, $\beta = .605$, $t = 7.62$, $p < 0.001$) accounts for 36.6% of the variance in Employee Job Performance. This means that perceived E-Training Efficiency has a positive impact on Employee Job performance, **supporting H1**.

H2: Perceived E-Training methods have a positive impact on employees' job performance.

Table 4: Linear Regression test of E-Training Methods against Employee Job performance

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.535	.287	.280	.51666		
ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	10.830	1	10.830	40.572	<.001
	Residual	26.961	101	.267		
	Total	37.791	102			
Coefficients						
Model		Standardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.867	.337		5.539	<.001
	E-Training Methods	.545	.086	.535	6.370	<.001

Dependent Variable: Employee Job Performance

Predictors: (Constant), E-Training Methods

A simple linear regression was performed to determine how much variation in Employee Job Performance is explained by perceived E-Training methods. By reviewing the ANOVA table, the findings showed that the model is significant ($P < .001$). According to the results of the model summary table, perceived E-Training methods ($R = .535$, $R^2 = .287$, $\beta = .535$, $t = 6.37$, $p < 0.001$) account for 28.7% of the variance in Employee Job Performance. This means that perceived E-Training methods have a positive impact on Employee Job performance, **supporting H2**.

H3: Perceived E-Training Environment has a positive impact on employees' job performance

Table 5: Linear Regression test of E-Training Environment against Employee Job performance

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.568	.323	.316	.50336		
ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.201	1	12.201	48.156	<.001
	Residual	25.590	101	.253		
	Total	37.791	102			
Coefficients						
Model		Standardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.856	.311		5.959	<.001
	E-Training Environment	.560	.081	.568	6.939	<.001

Dependent Variable: Employee Job Performance

Predictors: (Constant), E-Training Environment

A simple linear regression was performed to determine how much variation in Employee Job Performance is explained by the perceived E-Training environment. By

reviewing the ANOVA table, the findings showed that the model is significant ($P < .001$). According to the results of the model summary table, the perceived E-Training environment ($R = .568$, $R^2 = .323$, $\beta = .568$, $t = 6.93$, $p < 0.001$) accounts for 32.3% of the variance in Employee Job Performance. This means that the perceived E-Training environment has a positive impact on Employee Job performance, **supporting H3**.

After conducting the simple linear regression, the researcher wanted to perform multiple linear regression to determine which of the independent variables is the most significant predictor for the dependent variable.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Test

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square		Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.654	.428	.411		.46718	
ANOVA						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.184	3	5.395	24.717	<.001
	Residual	21.607	99	.218		
	Total	37.791	102			
Coefficients						
Model		Standardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.139	.339		3.360	.001
	E-Training Efficiency	.322	.115	.325	2.807	.006
	E-Training Methods	.162	.110	.159	1.476	.143
	E-Training Environment	.254	.104	.258	2.456	.016

Dependent Variable: Employee Job Performance

Predictors: (Constant), E-Training Efficiency, E-Training Methods, E-Training Environment

Multiple regression was performed to determine which dimension of the E-Training is the most significant predictor for Employee Job performance. By reviewing the ANOVA table, the findings showed that the model is significant ($P < .001$). The results indicate that perceived E-Training efficiency ($\beta = .325$, $t = 2.80$, $p < 0.001$) has the most impact on Employee Job performance, followed by perceived E-Training environment ($\beta = .258$, $t = 2.45$, $p < 0.016$).

5.5. Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results

Figure 2. The results of hypothesis testing

6. Discussion

The main results of this study have supported the three correlation hypotheses, as it concluded that E-training dimensions (Efficiency- Methods- Environment) positively affect the employees' job performance. This means that companies need to continue investing in the development of e-training infrastructure, especially after the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic, as companies' reliance on this type of training increased even after the epidemic subsided. So, technological progress and the mechanisms of globalization that the world is witnessing today impose on contemporary organizations to take care of their human resources by using the latest technology applications to provide them with valuable knowledge, skills, and capabilities to achieve their goals effectively. Therefore, organizations must focus their efforts on the optimal use of their employees through job satisfaction, continuous improvement in their functional performance, and creating the appropriate environment to motivate them to achieve the highest productivity.

The study revealed that E-training efficiency is the most influential dimension of employee performance, which is related to the quality of the content provided, and the eligibility of the trainer. Thus, companies should be eager in engaging qualified and experienced trainers in their field and have communication skills that qualify them to manage training programs effectively. Hence the importance of the Training Needs Assessment before starting the training program, as it helps in selecting the right people for the training programs, choosing the appropriate training style, level, and topics for them, and the suitable duration of the program to achieve the training objectives efficiently and productively. This finding is in line with a study by Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia (2016, 5), which indicated to the importance of E-training efficiency in influencing employee performance.

Moreover, the study also concluded that the E-training environment variable has received the second highest correlation to job performance, this finding confirms a study by Kamal, Aghbari & Atteia (2016, 6). On the other hand, the E-training methods variable has received the least impact on employee performance. This finding is not in line with a study by Asamoah & Avenorgbo (2021, 44), which indicated that the various methods used in E-training programs have a strong significant relationship with employee performance.

7. Conclusion

Improving job performance and increasing productivity is one of the most important goals that organizations aim at. These organizations have realized that human investment is the best way to achieve this goal, so they have focused on training their employees and developing their knowledge and functional skills. In general, E-Training not only leads to an increase in the productive and professional efficiency of employees but it is also considered one of the core factors that help in improving their sense of satisfaction and job security. Many organizations have realized this fact, so training programs are no longer limited to learning the necessary skills to increase productivity but are also concerned with educating employees in many fields related to their work and lives.

This study sheds light on the importance of E-Training, as its impact and applications have increased in recent years due to the development of communication and information technology, and the expansion of online training strategies and remote work. In recent years, e-training has become an important strategy that helps employees learn job-related competencies and other life communication skills. This has encouraged many business organizations to rely on the e-training system. This study concluded that the dimension of E-Training Efficiency (Content & Trainer) had the most impact on employee performance, followed by the E-Training Environment, and finally E-Training Methods. Therefore, organizations should focus on improving e-training methods to raise the level of their impact on employee performance, continue investing in e-training infrastructure, and attract qualified trainers who are able to design training programs and updated content that achieve the organization's goals and improve its competitiveness. In addition, provide a motivating work environment for career development and advancement.

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